

ISTM 6204

Information Technology Project Management

Project 1

Moldova - Disaster and Climate Risk Management Project

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1. Project Overview

1.1 Abstract

The Disaster and Climate, Risk Management Project, aims to improve the State Hydro-meteorological Service's ability to help Moldovan to predict extreme weather and develop the ability to face natural disasters. The whole project consists of four components: Component A: Severe weather forecasting capacity improvement. Component B: Disaster preparedness and emergency response construction. Component C: Climate risks in agriculture control. Component D: project management, which is the fiduciary support to implement the components as mentioned above. The parent project was built in November 2010 and conduct the first review in February 2013, primarily funded US\$ 10 million by International Development Assistance (IDA). Then in 2015, extra US\$ 2 million was added to meet financing gap arising for customized software for the Emergency Command Center (ECC), leading to extending the close date to September 30, 2016, to the need of developing customized software for the SHS, as well as associated staff training. The result indicates that the project development objective has achieved, leading to improvements in the economy, population, environment, the real-time observations system, Emergency Command Center construction and JIT communication platform infrastructure. However, some aspects are still waiting to be improved (World Bank 2010).

1.2 Project Objective

This Project object is to reinforce the capacity of SHS to predict extreme spot weather condition and assist Moldovan in preparation for natural disasters. In order to achieve the PDO, this project create timely and accurate weather monitor system, manage responses to disasters and help

individuals realize and adapt to natural hazards. In 2015, the revised scheme was introduced in due to the finance gap, resulting in achievements of some primary objectives adjusted respectively (World Bank 2010).

PDO Indicator

Indicator	Baseline	Target	Revised Target	Result
More forecast of weather	Forecast scale:5000 sq.km.	Reduce to 300 sq.km.		Completed at 09/15/2016
Lead-time Expansion	For severe weather(10min-1hour)	Expand to 12 hours	Expand to 3-6 hours	Completed at 09/15/2016
More coordinate response to emergencies	No related agencies	Emergency response drill	Emergency response drill shows capacity	Completed at 12/01/2015
Install Doppler Radar	No effective facilities	Improved forecast		Completed 06/04/2014
Now-casting tools & data collection	None for early warning system	Automated data in system for timely warnings		Completed (06/15/2016)
ECC establishment and user training	An additional floor but not stuff trained	ECC has been tested and at least 80 qualified employees	At least 90 trained.	Completed (06/04/2014)
Investment grants support	No adaption to climate risks	50 demonstration plots.		Completed 53 grants and 92 demonstration (06/04/2016)

1.3 Project Beneficiaries & Stakeholders

Project Beneficiaries:

- **The Government of Moldova:** The State Hydrometeorological Service(SHS), the State Department for Exceptional Situations, the Ministry of Agriculture and the Ministry of Environment strengthen their capacities to forecast and respond to severe weather.

- **Local:** Farmers benefitted from investment grants for tests aimed at increasing preventions about coping and adapting techniques to make the agriculture more resilient to adverse weather. Also, farmers who subscribed to the just-in-time communication platform improved their disaster responses (World Bank 2009).

Project Stakeholders:

- **UNDP and the Austrian Development Agency** supported the partnership between the Austrian Central Institute for Meteorology to share best practices on forecasting and early alarming, and to benefit communities prone to climate-related disasters.
- **The Czech Development Agency** assisted in the establishment of 11 automated hydrological posts on the river Prut.
- **MCC** established 18 automated hydrological posts on the Nistru.
- **The EIB** supported the Moldova Flood Protection Project to develop a flood protection master plan and an associated investment plan along with the SHS in flood controls (World Bank 2011).

2. Project Description

2.1 Project Cost and Financing

Component A: Severe weather forecasting capacity improvement. The total appraisal fund is US\$ 4.36 million. After the adding US\$ 5.18 million in phase II, the overall financing is US\$ 5.18 million. The funding in this components is utilized to finance training and equipment to develop early warning capabilities, install d radar technology, and strengthen data deficiencies.

Component B: Disaster preparedness and emergency response construction. The total appraisal fund is US\$ 2.45 million. With additional financing of US\$ 1.99 million, the total is US\$ 4.44 million. This component financed the study, design of an ECC, staff training and independent monitoring during emergencies.

Component C: Climate risks in agriculture control. Component. The total appraisal is US\$ 1.83 million. The final is US\$ 1.96 million after calculating additional financing of US\$ 0.13 million.

This financing supports advisory services, pilot testing awareness, and adverse weather-resilient techniques.

Component D: project management. US\$ 0.45 million at appraisal, additional financing of US\$ 0.25 million for a total of US\$ 0.77 million; US\$ 1.71 million. This component financed support for fiduciary and procurement functions of the Project Management Team (World Bank 2015)

2.2. Participating Organizations

- Meteorological Organization Eastern Europe Regional drought forecasting program.
- World Meteorological Organization's (WMO) strategy for Service Delivery.
- SHS develops weather-forecasting services targeted to public and commercial clients and builds the institutional capacity in line with the World Meteorological Organization (WMO).
- European Organization for the Exploitation of Meteorological Satellites (EUMETSAT) (World Bank 2011).

2.3 The Implementation

Two main factors that could influence the project implementation: implantation delays in strengthening severe weather forecasting and costs exceed the budgets for both weather forecasting and disaster preparedness improvement World Bank 2010.

Reinforce weather prediction

The project upgrades technical capacity, building access to global data for resolution and utilizing outputs analyzed from numerical models, resulting in sensitive weather parameters measurements. Due to the inconsistency in SHS's technical specification, the acquisition process delayed even though they had already implemented staff training. Too many changes indicated the weak association in management leadership, supervision, and controls. Delays reduced the

capacity for utilizing equipment in the building phase. Therefore, the stability of this building phase is at high risk.

Enhance disaster preparation

The project built two emergency drills as well as demonstration plots utilizing climate-resilient practices. The availability of the demonstration plots climate-resilient farming techniques is advertised extensively using media outlets.

The project expands the lead-time of weather warnings to users and improves lead time in severe weather warnings by more than half an hour. The capacity to coordinate response to emergencies strengthened.

The procurement and training took longer than the original plan. The Emergency Command Center was commissioned in August 2013 and needs extended time, which produced the most significant overrun budget to \$4.4 million, which finally supported by IDA and left funds. In the beginning, the project estimated US\$ 379,000 in construction, the actual costs were twice the estimate.

Initiate Adaptation to Climate Risks in Agriculture

The project installs Doppler Radar, with which the automated data integrated, and trained staff the way to utilized facilities. The plan establishes the Emergency Command Center(ECC) for state-of-the-art assist facility and around 90 ECC staff member trained in emergency management. The Committee for Exceptional Situation fully utilizes the Emergency Command Center.

The just-in-time communication platform contracted to National Rural Development Agency (ACSA) is on time and operational in 2012, resulting in integration among diversified systems. However, the system showed limitation due to the limited capacity in localized weather forecasts.

At the same time, the function to send messages to farmers constrained by the technical ability of the mobile operators. ACSA was contracted to implement the Adverse Weather Adaptation Advisory Services and win success through the upcoming Moldova Climate Adaptation Project. The interaction between organizations are valid and finally resulting in resilience to climate changes and assist 220 farmers to practice on their farms(World Bank 2015).

2.4 The Project Improvement

The project provided advanced forecasting equipment and training for SHS, as well as improving the capacity of DES by building ECC for Moldovan to response to natural, disasters, and quality of service. SHS and DES stressed the capacity improvements induced by WB-funded, which located radar on MOLDATSA for investment sustainability of MOLD ATLAS to build preparedness and response capacities through technical assistance and investments in equipment. The acquisition of Doppler radar had a positive impact on the safety of air flights from Moldova(World Bank 2009).

2.5 The Project Activities

Background Analysis

Between Romania and Ukraine, there is an inland country named Moldova with a population of about 3.5 million. As an agrarian country, Moldova's economic comparative advantage relies on its fertile soil and mild climate(World Bank 2009). Because of global climate trends and their geographical disadvantages, Moldova's relative benefits have been gradually reduced by extreme weather like frosts, hailstorms, and droughts, leading to significant losses in their economy and quality of life.

The project designed informed by South Eastern Europe Disaster Risk Mitigation and Adaption Program that identified hazard monitoring, climate change adaptation as issues requiring in the

region. To meet multiple system requirements, the project activities related to weather forecast had the interoperability of the acquired systems. Even though misunderstandings of the equipment utility happened at the beginning, the project finally integrated the procurements into modern production methods. With the unique combination from WB, Moldova can forecast and respond to natural disasters efficiently (World Bank 2011).

Assessment of the project design

Due to the precise objective to minimize economic and human losses by the monitor system for severe weather events, the project design cannot be complicated, and the components targeted limited and specific priority improvements improved country capacity to respond to climate risks. For the coherence in project management, the task team utilizes a project management that experienced with WB fiduciary procedures.

There was a high degree of commitment and active involvement from the participating in a situation at the design phase. The determination of the government of Moldova at entry level was high (World Bank 2015).

3. Project Outcomes

3.1 Project Performance

The World Bank Performance

Considering the time and scope to implementation challenges, the reporter can evaluate the performance of the World Bank as high. The World Bank, on the one hand, helped identify crucial areas to answer climate risks, on the other side reviewed fiduciary arrangements for compliance, evaluated the risk to the sustainability of the development outcome and secured a grant to strengthen the SHS service. However, the bank could have paid more attention to SHS's weakness. At the same time, the framework was captured the primary outputs and outcomes

positively. PMT employment across the three implementing agencies proved a useful and valuable arrangement to keep the project on track.

Brower Performance

The Government of Moldova strongly supported the project preparation of the project. However, there are reshuffles lag the implementation progress and lead to confusions in management leadership and direction. At some point, the SHS did not have a General Director for about eight months, and implementation halted with procurement backlog of up to \$2 million. After a two-year extension, the pace picked up again, and the project completed on a revised schedule (World Bank 2015).

3.2 Achievement of Project Development Objectives

Object 1: Reinforce Weather Preparation

Outcomes: the project achieves accurate and specific forecasting of weather conditions.

Object 2: Enhance Disaster preparation

Outcomes: The availability of the demonstration plots climate-resilient farming techniques advertised. The project expands the lead-time of weather warnings. The capacity to coordinate response to emergencies strengthened.

Object 3: Increase Practical Application

Outcomes: Data is automatically integrated, and the staff training. The plan establishes the Emergency Command Center (ECC) for state-of-the-art assist facility. The Committee for Exceptional Situation fully utilizes the Emergency Command Center (World Bank 2011).

3.3 Impacts of the Project

Positive:

Social Development

The project provides public the improved response by national emergency authorities to weather-related disasters, which benefits lives of rural residents, bring out improved life quality(World Bank 2010).

Institutional Strengthening

The project built three Moldovan institutions and provided advanced forecasting training on how to use it for SHS. To strengthen the capacity of the DES, designers conduct the project form a state-of-the-art Emergency Command Center and the Ministry of Agriculture and Food Industry to run pilot schemes to test modern and climate-responsive agriculture and Food Industry to run pilot schemes(World Bank 2011).

Negative:

At beginning, due to the unaffordable to the poor, the project missed the opportunity to explicitly integrate poverty and gender for the demonstration plots that piloted climate-resilient techniques, which could have provided valuable lessons on what methods/investments are affordable to the poor and which are beyond their reach(World Bank 2011).

4.Project Risks and Lessons Learned

4.1 Risk & Mitigation:

Risk Categories	Mitigation Process
1)Incremental costs associated with operation and maintenance the equipment	The government of Moldova will budget include the following Operations and Maintenance costs.
2)Low level of implementation capacity	The project team conduct the mid-term review of the status of the SHS and

	improve the ability to retain qualified staff.
3)The political risks associated with the hydrometeorological data.	The project team conducts the implementation of the follow-up GFDRR assisting the SHS.

(World Bank 2011).

4.2 Challenges and Lessons Learned

Efficient Plan: The strategic plans, operational and investment strategies are necessary as a guidance references for agencies because the frequent reshuffles happened a lot in volatile political environments of coalition governments, with which project could be stable and continuous(World Bank 2015).

Big Picture Ahead: It is necessary to keep the “bigger picture” as a service-oriented plan to be active for hydro-meteorological information needs. Ahead of the project, upfront assets should establish if the agency has streamlined forecast production processes to be best within and support a service producing process (World Bank 2010).

PPF funds: Before the project starts, the utilization of PPF funds could inform projects better and save valuable implementation time. At the same time, to use project management teams for compliance and coordination is practical in the early of the project to develop the organized understanding of the project for both PMT and other implementing agencies is high-qualified, reducing the misconceptions about roles and responsibilities(World Bank 2011).

Continuous Engagement: In Moldova, the DES management pursued discussion more vigorously, leading to the deficient required budget allocated immediately in the post-project

phases. Additionally, maintaining communication with the agency responsible for budgeting operations and maintenance of new equipment is critical to obtaining adequate resources.

Therefore, continuous engagement with the Ministry of Finance is necessary to support sufficient budget (World Bank 2011).

5. Project Opinion and Conclusions

The Project development objective has achieved. After the project, the economy, population, and environment improved caused by severe weather forecast system of State Hydrometeorological Service's(SHS) strengthened. The real-time observations system that is essential for monitoring the actual weather situation in an accurate and timely way are now available at SHS due to the availability of the advanced weather radar built to reach state-of-the-art. At the same time, the Emergency Command Center is functional, and the staff training. JIT communication platform created an efficient way for farmers and rural communities to receive operative supports and alerts.

Activities related to completion by SHS for putting into services of the equipment, human capacity building, and maintenance of performance should continue in the future. For example, the final Lead time for severe weather warnings only achieves 3-6 hours, which is 6 hours less than the formally revised target. At the same time, the interoperation of projects to build a functional system defined. For droughts and frosty weather, the activities should extend for farmers' adaption. The least cover of the project is stakeholder engagement such as User Interface Platform, and the best protection relies on Capacity Development(World Bank 2011).At the same time, this project limits on the unclear extent to coordination among projects for more significant impact. For financing, the level of international investment or support is obscure because the inaccurate financial budget influences the project process.

For the implementation delays, the team could have utilized upfront design on institutional strengthening. The project process would be better if the team checked the suitability of the off-the-shelf software for the ECC. SHS did not have a General Director for about eight months, and implementation halted with procurement backlog of up to \$2 million(World Bank 2011) After a two-year extension, the pace picked up again, and the project completed on a revised schedule.

6. Biography

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